

Influence of Geographical Location on the Achievement of Senior Secondary Students in Calculus Using Guided Discovery Learning Strategy in Jam'a Local Government of Kaduna State.

¹Na'allah Zakaria, ²Na'allah Ifeoluwa Grace, ³Chep Habilah Magaji

^{1,2,3}Kaduna State College of Education Gidan Waya.

zakarianaallaa@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examined the influence of geographical location on the achievement of senior secondary students in calculus using guided discovery learning strategy in Jema'a Local Government of Kaduna state, Nigeria. It specifically examined it's in on: students' achievement in Urban and Rural senior secondary, on gender and its potency in improving the learner's achievement in mathematics using guided discovery learning strategy. A quasi-experimental design was used due to the fact that intact classes were assigned to both schools. The sample drawn was 160 senior secondary school two (SSS2) students from two (2) public schools. Both schools were taught using the guided discovery strategy. PRE and POST-TEST results on Calculus Achievement Test (CAT) were collected after the conduct of the test, and analysis were made using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The Reliability of 0.68 index was gotten for the instrument. The descriptive statistics (mean) results were used in answering the three (3) research questions while inferential statistics (ANCOVA) results were used in testing the three(3) corresponding hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. From the result obtained, null hypothesis(1) was retained, indicating that there was no significant influence of geographical location using guided discovery learning strategy on students' achievement in calculus. However, null hypothesis two (2) was rejected indicating that there was a significant influence of gender in favor of male on the achievement of students in calculus. By the findings of this study, it implies that guided discovery learning strategy has the potency of improving the achievement of students in calculus without any bias to school location. It was therefore recommended that teachers should make the teaching and learning of mathematics interactive and activity- based approach, and encourages female gender to participate more in learning activities during mathematics classes in order to scale over inferiority complex. However, Ministries of education at both federal and state levels should periodically asides regular workshops for teachers' development and make it a platform of assessing and reviewing the impact of teaching strategies.

Keyword: Senior Secondary Students, Calculus, Pre-Test, Post Test, Location, and Achievements.

Introduction

Mathematics is both necessary and compulsory subject at the pre-tertiary education level of learning, and remains an indispensable entry requirement into tertiary institutions in the country (Nigeria). Its importance and relevance permeate extensively within and outside the walls of the classroom. Certain qualities that are nurtured by mathematic are power of reasoning, creativity, spatial thinking, critical thinking, problem-solving ability and effective communication skills. These and many more make the subject the cradle of all creations, without which the world can in no way develop scientifically. Calculus is a branch of mathematics that explores variables and how they change by looking at them in infinitely small pieces called infinitesimal. The beauty and application calculus is not just in mathematics alone but it holds an incredible power over the physical world by modeling and controlling system. It is the language of medical experts, scientists, engineers, statisticians, physicists and economists. If a quantity or system is changing we can use mathematical modeling of calculus to analyze a system, find an optimal solution and predict the future. Motion, electricity, heat and light, harmonics and acoustics, astronomy, radioactive decay reaction rates, birth and death rates, costs and revenues, all of these can be modeled beautifully using calculus. Calculus was one of those topics that the senior secondary students only contended with it at the point of their Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) in the past, but had recently been introduced and integrated into the Senior Secondary school mathematics curriculum in Nigeria.

Achievement in mathematics is a function of quite a number of factors such as students' interest, instructional strategy, and availability of relevant instructional materials and the geographical location of the schools. Geographical locations connote rural or urban areas. Orji (2013) explained that many students in the interior villages struggled with the challenge of walking a long distance to schools. While learners within the urban settings are conveyed to schools by vehicles, and enjoy minimum travelling distance to acquire education. Such could among other factors contribute to the poor students' achievement in mathematics within the rural area. In an attempt to investigate the influence of geographical location on the academic performance of learners. Frederick (2011) observed a significant difference in urban-rural performance and that location exerted a measure of significance on the achievement of students in Agricultural science achievement test (ASAT). In consonance with Frederick findings, owoeye and yara (2011) find a significant difference in the academic achievement of students among urban and rural in senior school certificate examination in Ekiti State. Contrary to the findings of others, chinedu (2008) who carried out a study on environmental awareness and attitude of secondary schools students in Owerri Imo State, had his findings revealed that gender and location do not have influence on students' achievement. From the findings of various empirical studies on the influence school location, their submissions are both divergent and contradictory. Therefore, it becomes

critically necessary to carry out further research to affirmed or annul inclusive challenge on the influence of interaction of schools location (urban and rural) on the academic achievement secondary schools students in mathematics using guided discovery learning strategy.

Purpose of the Study

The study aims at determining the influence of geographical location on the achievement senior secondary students in calculus using guided discovery learning strategy. Specifically the study intends achieve the following objectives:

1. Examine the influence of geographical location on the achievement of senior secondary two students in calculus using guided discovery strategy.
2. Determine the influence of geographical location on gender achievement in calculus using guided discovery learning strategy.
3. Examine the efficacy of guided discovery learning strategy in improving the achievement of senior secondary two students in calculus.

Research Questions

- 1 What is the of guided discovery learning strategy on the achievement scores of Senior Secondary II students in calculus based on school location?
- 2 What is the influence of geographical location on Senior Secondary II students' achievement in calculus based on gender?
- 3 What is the influence of guided discovery learning strategy on the pretest and posttest achievement mea score of Senior Secondary II students in calculus?
- 4

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

- 1 There is no significant difference in the achievement mean score between urban and rural learners using guided discovery learning strategy.
- 2 There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught using guided discovery strategy.
- 3 There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest achievement mean score of experimental group using guided discovery learning strategy.

Research Design

The following research questions guided the study:

The quasi experimental design was adopted for this study. This is because, in order to avoid a disruption of school activities and arrangements, random assignment of subjects from different classrooms into the sample was not possible. Intact classrooms were used.

Population and Sample

The population for the study involved all the Senior Secondary two students in Jama’a Local Government Area, which has seventeen 17 Senior Secondary schools with a total population of 1200. Consisting of 750 male’s students and 450 female students. The sample of 160 students was randomly selected from the total population.

Instrument of Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was Calculus Achievement Test (CAT), which was adopted by the researcher, using senior secondary two mathematics text book as a guide.

Results and Discussion

Answering Research Questions

Research Question One

What is the influence of geographical location on the achievement mean scores of rural and urban senior secondary II students in calculus?

Table1; Post-test Achievement Scores of Urban and Rural Students’ in the Experimental Group

Group	School Location	Post-test			
		N	Mean	SD	\bar{x} - Difference
Experimental	Urban	100	60.27	11.36	0.47
	Rural	60	60.69	12.08	

Table1 above reveals the mean and standard deviation results on the effect of geographical location on the achievement mean scores of rural and urban senior secondary II student’s achievement in calculus. The result shows that the posttest mean score for urban students is 60.27 with a standard deviation of 11.36, while the achievement mean score of students from rural area is 60.69 with standard deviation of 12.08. The findings show that urban students had almost same achievement mean score (60.27) as the rural school students (60.69) after treatment using guided discovery learning strategy with a mean difference of 0.47. This indicates that guided discovery learning strategy does increase the achievement scores of both urban and rural students’ in calculus, therefore school location does not make a difference.

Research Questions Two

What is the influence of guided discovery learning strategy on Senior Secondary II students’ achievement in calculus based on gender?

Table2: Post-test Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students’ in Experimental Group

Group	Gender	N	Post-test		Difference
			Mean	SD	
Experimental	Male	116	62.39	11.44	3.82
	Female	44	59.57	11.39	

Table2 above reveals the mean and standard deviation results on the effect of guided discovery learning strategy on Senior Secondary students’ achievement based on gender in calculus. The result shows that the posttest mean score for male is 62.39 with a standard deviation of 11.44, while the achievement mean score for female is 59.57 with standard deviation of 11.39. The findings show that male students in the experimental group had a higher achievement mean score of 62.39 than the male students of 59.57 after treatment using guided discovery learning strategy with a mean difference of 3.82. This shows that guided discovery learning strategy does increase more of male students’ achievement mean scores in calculus than female students.

Research Questions Three

What is the influence of guided discovery learning strategy on the pretest and posttest achievement

mean score of Senior Secondary II students in calculus?

Table3: Pre-test and Post-test Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students' in Experimental Group.

Group	Test	N	Mean	SD	\bar{x} - Gain
Experimental	Pre-test	160	37.48	10.48	25.07
	Post-test	160	62.55	11.98	

The Table3 above reveals the mean and standard deviation results of pre-test and posttest mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary II students in calculus in the experimental group. The result shows that the pre-test mean score is 37.48 with a standard deviation of 10.48, while the post-test mean score is 62.55 higher than the pre-test mean score with a mean gain of 25.07, indicating that there was improvement in the performance of students after treatment. This shows that guided discovery learning strategy does increase students' achievement mean scores in Calculus.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the achievement mean score of urban and rural students taught calculus using guided discovery strategy.

Table4: ANCOVA Result on Effect of School Location on Achievement of SS11 Students in the Experimental Group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	66.424 ^a	2	33.212	.243	.785	.006
Intercept	18575.153	1	18575.153	135.798	.000	.632
Pre-achievement	66.396	1	66.396	.485	.488	.006
School Location	1.454	1	1.454	.011	.918	.000
Error	10806.028	84	136.785			
Total	310771.000	98				
Corrected Total	10872.451	97				

a. R Squared = .006 (Adjusted R Squared = -.019)

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to determine if there is a significant effect of School location on achievement of SSII students taught calculus using guided discovery strategy. Table-shows that the main effect of urban school students yielded ($M = 60.27$; $SD = 11.36$) and rural school students ($M = 60.69$ $SD = 12.08$); $F(1,79) = .011$, $p > 0.05$, since the p-value of 0.918 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was upheld, indicating that there is no significant effect of school location on the achievement of students taught calculus using guided discovery strategy. Hence, guided discovery can help improve the achievement of both urban and rural school students in calculus.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught calculus using guided discovery strategy.

Table5: ANCOVA Result on Effect of Gender on Achievement of SS11 Students in the Experimental Group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	628.705 ^a	2	314.353	2.424	.095	.058
Intercept	18924.528	1	18924.528	145.946	.000	.649
Pre-achievement	146.978	1	146.978	1.133	.290	.014
Gender	563.736	1	563.736	4.348	.040	.052
Error	10243.746	79	129.668			
Total	310771.000	82				
Corrected Total	10872.451	81				

a. R Squared = .058 (Adjusted R Squared = .034)

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to determine if there is a significant effect of gender on achievement of SSII students taught calculus using guided discovery strategy. Table5 - shows that the main effect of male yielded ($M = 62.39$; $SD = 11.44$) and female ($M = 59.57$; $SD = 11.39$); $F(1, 79) = .011$, $p < 0.05$, since the p-value of 0.04 is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there was a significant effect of gender on the achievement of students taught calculus using guided discovery strategy. Hence, we can say that guided discovery can help improve achievement in calculus in favor of male students.

Discussion

The main aim of this study was to investigate the influence of geographical location on students' achievement in calculus using guided discovery learning strategy, and the findings from Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of post-test mean score of hypothesis one revealed that both urban and rural schools of the experimental group exposed to guided discovery learning strategy performed significantly better and almost same, this could be seen in table1. The findings of this study is consistent with those of Abari and Ikyule (2021) where they found that guided discovery approach was more effective than conventional approach on students' knowledge acquisition process and achievement in mathematics. The study also showed from the post-test mean score of hypothesis two evident in Table that there was significant effect of gender on the achievement of students taught calculus using guided discovery learning strategy with male students performing better than females' students. The finding contradicts that of Akanmu and Olubusuyi (2023) where it was found that gender has no effects on the achievement of students taught mathematics using guided discovery learning strategy, however consistent with the findings Of Isa (2018) where it was found that gender has significant effect on the performance of students in mathematics taught using guided discovery learning strategy.

The result In table 9 based on treatment on experimental group inferred from hypothesis three revealed that students performed better in calculus when taught with guided discovery learning strategy. Hence the use of guided discovery learning strategy has potency of improving the performance of Senior Secondary students in WAEC, and eventually afford the students with an opportunity of further capacity building, and improves the economy of the country.

This finding agrees with the findings of Akanmu and Olubusuyi (2023) whose findings showed that students performed better in mathematics with guided discovery learning strategy than conventional method.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research, the following conclusion is drawn;
Findings from this study have shown that there was no significant difference in the achievement of senior secondary II students in calculus based on geographical location taught using guided discovery learning strategy. The study has shown the potency of guided discovery strategy in improving students' achievement in calculus. Equally, findings from the present study have also shown that gender has significant role to play in the performance of the students. This implies that guided discovery learning strategy stimulate every student at all locations to better performance in calculus.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should make the teaching – learning of mathematics an interactive and active- based one for students. Since guided discovery learning strategy was found to improve achievement in calculus.
2. Teachers should encourage and employ professional skills available to improve the performance of female students promote interaction in mathematics classes.
3. Rural schools should be given opportunities to participate in inter-schools quiz competitions with urban schools, since it was revealed from this studies that school location is not a limitation to the performance of students in calculus.
4. Ministries of education at both federal and state levels should periodically organize workshops for teachers’ development and make it a platform of assessing and reviewing the impact of teaching strategies.
5. National Mathematical Centre which has the sole responsibility of training and developing high level personnel in mathematics science, supporting activities leading to the improvement of teaching and learning of mathematics at all level, should by the findings of this study organize workshops, seminars and conferences to promote effectiveness in teaching and learning of calculus among secondary schools.

References

- Abamba, I. (2021). The effects of school location on students' academic achievement in senior secondary physics based the 5E learning cycle in delta state, Nigeria. *International Journal on Mathematics Science and Technology Education*, 9(1), 56-76.
- Akanmu, M.A. & Fajemidagba, M.O. (2023) Guided discovery learning strategy and senior school students performance in mathematics in Ejigbo, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(4), 82-89.
- Arul, A. S. (2012). School Environment and Academic Performance of Standard six Students. *Journal of Educational and Industrial Studies in the world*, 3(2), 22- 30.
- Azuka, B.F., Olatoji, J., & Okwuoza (2013). Difficulty level of topics in the new senior secondary school mathematics curriculum as perceived by mathematics teachers of federal unity schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 1(1), 20-35.
- Bature, I. M. (2012). The role of mathematics in the development of Nigerian Economy. A paper presented at the 31 Annual Conference of the Nigerian Mathematical Association (NMS), Held at Department of mathematics, Ahmadu Bello University , Zaria-Nigeria between 2 oct- 5 oct, 2012.
- Frederick, E. O. (2011). Influence of sex and school location on students' achievement in Agricultural science. *African Journal of Science Technology and Mathematics Education (AJSTME)*, 1(1), 96-101
- Isa, S.G. (2018). The effect of school location on senior secondary school mathematics students' performance in Gaya zonal education area of Kano State. *Journal of Mathematics*, 14(2) 48-50.
- Orji, E. I. (2013). Effect of cognitive conflict instructional model on students'' conceptual change and attention in temperature and heat. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis. University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Owoeye, J. S. (2011). School location and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 5(7), 112-116.